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Abstract: The presence of educational and educational elements in the process of physical education leads to consider it as a whole pedagogical process. Each of the mentioned elements will appear differently depending on the task.

Key words: physical education, school, method, exercises.

In the process of performing physical exercises, it even affects the mental state of the participants, their emotions, will, and morals. Due to these, the necessary conditions for solving the educational tasks have been created. The presence of both educational and pedagogical elements in the process of physical education leads to consider it as a whole pedagogical process. Each of the mentioned elements will appear differently depending on the task.

Physical education reflects both the laws of physical development and the social laws of physical education. The use, character and method of social laws of physical education are actually derived from the economic and political structure of the society. This gives physical education a social character, and in a class society, education is subordinated to the interests of the ruling classes. Physical education is an eternal category, in the sense that this direction of education has existed since the beginning of society, and such a system continues as one of the necessary conditions of social production and human life (A.D. Novikov, 1959).

The unique feature of physical education as a social phenomenon is that it can serve as a means of developing human physical abilities in society, and at the same time it can have a strong impact on his spiritual development. This feature is a special sign of physical education that applies equally to everyone. But in the real

life of the society, there is no physical education outside of concrete historical conditions. In each socio-economic formation, a specific historical type of physical education develops.

Physical training. There are three main directions in physical education, and human physical education is carried out on the basis of these frameworks. They are general physical training, professional physical training, sports training. General physical training is aimed at strengthening the body, acquiring a wide range of movement skills and abilities, and developing basic movement qualities that serve as a basis for subsequent special training.

For the purpose of general physical training, all kinds of means of physical education, various physical exercises, healing forces of nature and hygienic factors are used. General physical training is carried out at all stages of physical education more often in the school physical education system, mass physical culture works and through individual forms of physical exercise. Vocational physical training is a specialized, specific type of physical training and a process focused on preparing for defensive activities. In this, mainly, types of physical exercises that are close to the craft or profession are used. The use of profession-oriented physical training accelerates the process of acquiring movement skills, increases the productivity of the worker, improves the resistance of the body to the harmful factors of the external environment.

The distinction between general and professional physical fitness is conditional to a certain extent, and both areas complement each other. Sports training represents a special direction in physical education. Its task is to ensure that a person achieves high results in a chosen sport. In physical education, sports fitness is related to the improvement of the functional capabilities of the body, high sports results become a criterion for evaluating people's physical fitness and are widely used as a goal for physical education.

Physical culture is a set of achievements in the creation and rational use of special

tools, methods and conditions for the purposeful realization of the physical development of the members of the society.

Physical culture is a part of general culture, its rise is inextricably linked to the level of social and economic development of society. Physical culture is a product of specific historical conditions. Each socio-economic formation is characterized by the culture of the members of the society, and it remains the wealth and property of the entire nation at a certain period of society's development, and remains a common and mandatory condition for the all-round perfection of the individual. Among the main concepts of the theory of physical education, physical culture (physiculpture) is a broad, comprehensive concept, and physical education as a component of the concept of "physical culture" includes a pedagogical process with three different directions (B.A. Ashmarin). School physical education is a set of material and spiritual resources created and used by society for physical training of children.

Material wealth means various sports facilities, special equipment, equipment, materials, and the level of physical maturity (sports achievements) of members of society. Moral wealth is the moral, scientific, organizational, practical and special scientific achievements created and shaped by the education system. Through physical education, any person acquires the content of physical culture worthy of him, and the achievement of this field becomes his personal property (wealth).

Physical culture performs certain services in the development of society:

- determining the rational standard (norms) of human activity;
- the service of collecting (news) cultural information about physical culture and mediates its transmission and distribution from generation to generation;
- formation of interpersonal communication, mutual communication (communicative) relations;
- (aesthetics) service related to meeting the demand of the aesthetics of movement of the person;
- a (biological) service related to satisfying a person's natural need for constant

movement and ensuring the necessary level of physical fitness for everyday life. The service of physical culture as a base is the basis of the so-called classification of physical culture - sport, practical health. In return for the physical knowledge, physical development, and physical fitness of a member of the society, the asset creates the ground for the achievement of physical maturity necessary for vital activity or the foundation of physical culture. Depending on the age of the participants, physical development, training, changing and acquiring specific characteristics.

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